

MaxEnt, ln(Probability) and the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Power Law Distributions Part II

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In Part I, we examined how a recipe for MaxEnt (maximum entropy) usually includes the constraint $\sum_i e_i P(e_i/T)$ and possibly a second constraint $\sum_i P(e_i)$. This leads to a recipe for the entropy such that $dS/dP = a + be_i/T$ ((A)) where a and b are constants, S being a function of $P(e_i/T)$. We saw that in both the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Power Law distributions, dS/dP is strictly a function of $\ln(P)$, which is called information in information theory. We then differentiated ((A)) with respect to $1/T$ to see what distributions appear if S is a function of $\ln(P)$ alone and saw the emergence of the MB and Power Law solutions.

In this note, we consider the Zwanzig differential equation (from (1)) which includes random noise in the form of a variance function $D(x,p)$. The power law distribution is a solution of this equation. We examine the Zwanzig equation to see exactly what condition needs to hold for any general solution (for a constant coefficient of friction for simplicity) and find the relation: $1 = D \frac{d}{dy} \ln(P)$ ((B)) where $y = a + be_i/T$. Thus $\ln(P)$ and its derivative which appears in Fisher's information are key pieces. Instead of differentiating the MaxEnt equation ((A)) by $1/T$, we argue that differentiation by e_i/T leads to ((B)) i.e. the key solution portion of the Zwanzig equation. Thus we link maximum entropy (albeit a derivative of this equation) to the solution of the Zwanzig equation for the MB and Power Law distributions.

MaxEnt

The maximization of entropy subject to constraints seems to be a key idea in statistical mechanics. It, however, also gives rise to a recipe because given a probability distribution $P(e_i/T)$ one may solve for $e_i/T = F(P)$. Next, one may integrate with respect to dP so that the derivative (d/dP from the maximization of entropy) yields e_i/T which matches $d/dP e_i/T P(e_i)$ from the usual energy constraint. One may generalize e_i/T to $a + be_i/T$ where a and b are constants by including the constraint $\sum_i P(e_i) = 1$. Thus, formally MaxEnt yields:

$$dS/dP = a + be_i/T = y \quad ((1)) \quad (y \text{ is a variable})$$

Maxwell-Boltzmann and Power Law Distributions and dS/dP Strictly a Function of $\ln(P)$

$\ln(P)$ is called information in information theory and in Part I we showed that in both the MB and Power Law cases, dS/dP is strictly a function of $\ln(P)$. This means taking $d/d(1/T)$ of ((1)) by writing $d/d\ln(P) dS/dP \ln(P)/d(1/T) = be_i$, that $d\ln(P)/d(1/T) = dP/dy / P$ (be_i). Thus, two immediate solutions are:

$$((2a)) \quad dP/dy = P \quad \text{and} \quad d/d\ln(P) dS/dP = 1 \quad \text{which yields the MB distribution OR}$$

((2b)) P is a power law so that dP/dy lowers the power of y by 1 and $d/d\ln(P) dS/dP$ has to increase it by 1 and bring in a constant i.e. $1/\text{power}$. This leads to the Power Law distribution. Explicitly: $P(e_i/T) = \text{constant} (1 - ke_i/T)^{1/k}$ ((3)).

Zwanzig Equation

A completely independent approach to finding a power law distribution is to solve the Zwanzig differential equation presented in (1). No mention of entropy or its maximization subject to constraints appears. The idea is to have Newtonian type equations with friction $g(p,x)$ and a probabilistic noise term $n(x,p,t)$ i.e.

$$dx/dt = p/m \quad \text{and} \quad dp/dt = -dV/dx - g(x,p)p + n(x,p,t) \quad ((4))$$

$$\langle n \rangle = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \langle nn \rangle = 2 D(x,p) \delta(t_1 - t) \quad ((5))$$

The Zwanzig equation is then :

$$d/dt \text{ partial density}(x,p,t) = -p/m \text{ d density}/dx \text{ partial} + d/dp(\text{partial}) \{ dV/dx + g(x,p)p \} + d/dp \text{ partial} D \text{ d/dp partial density} \quad ((6))$$

Where $P(e/T) = \text{density}(x,p,t)$ and $e = pp/2m + V(x)$

In (1), a solution of ((6)) for $d/dt \text{ partial density} = 0$ is given as:

$$\text{density} = P(ei/T) = C (1 - ke/T)^{1/k} \quad \text{if} \quad D = gm/T (1-ke/T) \quad ((7))$$

If one considers $g(x,p)$, the friction coefficient, to be constant for simplicity, one may focus on d/dp terms because: $-p/m \text{ d density}/dx \text{ partial}$ cancels with $dV/dx \text{ d density}/dp$. Thus a solution requires:

$$d/dp \text{ partial} \{ g p P + D(x,p) d/dp P \} = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad g p P + D(x,p) d/dp P = \text{constant} \quad ((8))$$

If $\text{constant} = 0$ and $y = a + be/T$, then:

$$gP = -D dP/dy (1/m) \quad \text{or} \quad gm = -D d \ln(P)/ dy \quad ((9))$$

((9)) includes $\ln(P)$, which is information from information theory and its derivative with respect to y which appears in Fisher's information. Solving the Zwanzig equation for g constant is equivalent to solving ((9)).

((9)) is very similar to the MaxEnt equation ((1)) differentiated with respect to be_i/T if dS/dP is strictly a function of $\ln(P)$, which as we argued in Part I, leads to either the MB or Power Law distribution.

An immediate solution of ((9)) is to have $P = \exp(C_1 y)$. Then D is constant and one has the MB solution with $C_1 y = -e/T$.

Like in the MaxEnt case, a second solution involves a power law. dP/dy lowers the power by 1 and D proportional to y raises it and brings in the constant $1/\text{power}$.

Thus taking the derivative $d/d(e/T)$ of the maximum entropy equation ((1)) is mathematically equivalent to solving the Zwanzig equation for a constant friction coefficient g . (Even if $g(x,p)$, the power law is still the solution and D does not change except that g is no longer a constant.)

Thus we argue that there seems to be a close connection between the Zwanzig equation, which does not seem to introduce entropy explicitly, and the idea of entropy maximization with respect to an energy constraint (and possibly a $\sum_i P(e_i) = 1$ constraint) if dS/dP is strictly a function of $\ln(P)$, information.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Part I we argued that the recipe based entropy maximization equation $dS/dP = a+be/T$, when differentiated with respect to $1/T$ or e/T with the assumption that dS/dP is strictly a function $\ln(P)$, leads to the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Power Law distributions.

In (1), a seemingly independent approach to finding the power law (and MB) distributions is presented in terms of a Zwanzig differential equation which does not use entropy explicitly. We show that for a constant friction coefficient, the Zwanzig condition may be equivalent to $gm = -D d \ln(P)/ dy$ where $y=a+be/T$. This equation is, in turn, equivalent to the derivative of the MaxEnt equation assuming dS/dP is a function strictly of $\ln(P)$ and so yields both the MB and Power Law distributions. Thus, we conclude that the Zwanzig equation for a constant friction coefficient is essentially equivalent to taking the derivative of the MaxEnt condition if dS/dP is strictly a function of $\ln(P)$.

References

1. Ran, G. and Du, J. Are power law distributions an equilibrium distribution or a stationary nonequilibrium distribution? (2013 or later) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1403.5441.pdf>